

PREPARATION OF SOME THIAZOLE DYES OF DOEBNER VIOLET TYPE

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4-Aryl-2-aminothiazoles, prepared from ketones and thioureas, were condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of HCl to yield di-(4-aryl-2-aminothiazyl-5-)-phenylmethanes. These were oxidised by lead dioxide in acid solution to the corresponding carbinols and then by oxalic acid and ammonium oxalate to the corresponding dyes of Doebner violet type. As dyes they are inferior to Malachite green.

In view of the significant use of thiazoles in therapy and as intermediates in the synthesis of cyanine dyes and that of triphenylmethane dyes as dyestuffs and also in medicine, it was considered of interest to prepare some dyes from thiazoles, analogous to triphenylmethane dyestuffs. Traumann (*Annalen*, 1888, 249, 50) made unsuccessful attempts to prepare a Thiazole green corresponding to Malachite green or Thiophene green. According to him, trithiazylmethane dyes would not exist, due, probably to the absence of *para* position in the azoles. He failed to obtain any dye by joint oxidation of thiazylamines with methylthiazylamine by the action of mercuric chloride. This view was, however, disputed by several workers who regarded the amino group in 2-aminothiazoles, for all practical purposes, as *para* to position-5, basing their argument on the fact that sulphur in cyclic union as equivalent of CH=CH group. That the amino group in 2-position in 2-aminothiazoles activates the carbon atom in position-5 is supported by several experimental facts like coupling or condensation with chloro-sulphonic acid (Faith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2068).

In support of their assumptions, Bogert and Chertcoff have successfully condensed 2-aminothiazoles with aromatic aldehydes in presence of hydrochloric acid to afford monoaryl-dithiazylmethanes. Such condensations may also be effected with 2-aminothiazoles carrying alkyl groups instead of aryls in position-4, indicating that the above condensations are not dependent on any aryl group in that position and that such a group does not participate in the reaction and that therefore the attachment is at position-5. It appeared to us of interest to verify the observation of Bogert and Chertcoff with 2-amino-4-naphthylthiazole and others in our attempts to prepare some interesting thiazole analogues of triphenylmethane dyes.

In the present work, five different 2-aminothiazoles having different substituents in position-4 have been studied. These were first condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of hydrochloric acid. Di-(4-aryl-2-aminothiazyl-5-)-phenylmethanes were obtained from which the corresponding carbinols and dyes were prepared. The reactions proceed as formulated below :

(R=simple or substituted aryl radical)

The leuco-bases, so obtained, are generally pale yellow or slightly grey in colour; the carbinols are red-black and the dyes (oxalates) are deep green-black. Comparison of certain properties of these new compounds with those of triphenylmethane derivatives of analogous structure discloses very interesting resemblances. Although of Doebner violet type, in the sense that the thiazole amino groups are unalkylated, these compounds afford green dyestuffs.

The dyeing characteristics of these dyes with respect to cotton are being studied. Study of the substantivity of these to cotton is also proposed to be carried out by the ultraviolet light absorption method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Di-(4-2-naphthyl-2-aminothiazyl-5)-phenylmethane (I).—A mixture of 4-naphthyl-2-aminothiazole (4.3 g.), benzaldehyde (0.93 g.) and HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) was refluxed for 5 hours at 145°. The mixture was then cooled and basified with NH₄OH. When diluted with water, the leuco-base was precipitated as a fine light yellow powder which was purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 165° (decomp.), yield 70%. (Found: N, 40.52; S, 11.95. C₂₈H₂₄N₄S₂ requires N, 40.37; S, 11.85 per cent).

Carbinol Base (II) of (I).—To a cooled solution of the leuco-base (I, 2.7 g.) in HCl (1.2 g.) and alcohol (100 c.c.) 2 c.c. of 40% acetic acid was added, followed by lead dioxide (1.25 g.) and the mixture was stirred continuously at 5°. After 3 hours, when the oxidation was complete, the mixture was filtered and an excess of ammonium

hydroxide was added to the filtrate. The latter was diluted when a precipitate appeared. This was kept overnight, filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140° (decomp.), yield 60%. (Found: S, 11.06. $C_{33}H_{24}ON_4S_2$ requires S, 11.51 per cent).

Oxalate Dye (III) derived from (II).—To a solution of (II, 2.4 g.) in 10 c.c. of acetone an aqueous solution of oxalic acid (1.2 g.) and ammonium oxalate (0.12 g.) was added. The colour of the solution changed immediately from brown to green. On evaporating off the acetone the dye was filtered and washed with water. It was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol as a dark green powder, m.p. 170° (decomp.), yield 60%. (Found: S, 8.92. $C_{66}H_{44}N_8S_4 \cdot 3C_2H_2O_4$ requires S, 9.51 per cent).

Di-(4-p-tolyl-2-aminothiazyl-5)-phenylmethane (IV) was prepared from 4-p-tolyl-2-aminothiazole (3.66 g.), benzaldehyde (0.93 g.) and HCl (conc., 8 c.c.) as in the above case. The product was isolated from the alcoholic solution by dilution with water after basification with NH_4OH and was crystallised from alcohol in greyish yellow powder, m.p. 247° (decomp.), yield 90%. (Found: S, 13.49. $C_{27}H_{24}N_4S_2$ requires S, 13.67 per cent).

Carbinol base (V) was prepared by oxidation of the leuco-base (IV, 2.3 g.) with PbO_2 (1.2 g.) in HCl (1.2 g.), alcohol (100 c.c.) and 40% acetic acid (2 c.c.). The base was isolated as before as a pale brown precipitate when crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 152° (decomp.), yield 85%. (Found: S, 13.02. $C_{27}H_{24}ON_4S_2$ requires S, 13.22 per cent).

Dye (oxalate) (VI) was prepared from (V, 2.1 g.), dissolved in acetone (10 c.c.) by treatment with an aqueous solution of oxalic acid (1.2 g.) and ammonium oxalate (0.12 g.). It was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol as a green-black powder, m.p. 149° (decomp.) yield 65%. (Found: S, 11.09. $C_{54}H_{44}N_8S_4 \cdot 3C_2H_2O_4$ requires S, 10.64 per cent).

Di-(4-p-chlorophenyl-2-aminothiazyl-5)-phenylmethane (VII) was prepared from 4-p-chlorophenyl-2-aminothiazole (4.1 g.), benzaldehyde (0.93 g.) and HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) and purified by crystallisation from alcohol, as a very light yellow powder, m.p. 172-74° (decomp.), yield 80%. (Found: S, 13.04. $C_{25}H_{18}N_4S_2Cl_2$ requires S, 12.57 per cent).

Carbinol base (VIII) of (VII) and the Dye (oxalate) (IX).—The leuco-base was oxidised to the carbinol (m.p. 114°, decomp.) by lead dioxide and hydrochloric acid, from which the dye (oxalate) was prepared. The latter was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol as a dark green powder which decomposed with swelling above 160°, yield 60%. (Found: S, 10.25. $C_{50}H_{32}N_8S_4Cl_4 \cdot 3C_2H_2O_4$ requires S, 9.96 per cent).

Di-(4-p-methoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazyl-5)-phenylmethane (X) was prepared from 4-p-methoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole (3.8 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.93 g.) as in the previous cases and purified by crystallisation from alcohol as pale greyish yellow small needles, m.p. 196° (decomp.), yield 90%. (Found: S, 12.52. $C_{27}H_{24}O_4N_4S_2$ requires S, 12.80 per cent).

Carbinol Base (XI) and Dye (oxalate) (XII).—From the above leuco-base, the carbinol was prepared as described in the analogous cases above, m.p. 128-30° (decomp.), yield 75%.

The dye (oxalate) was prepared from the carbinol (XI) by the action of oxalic acid and ammonium oxalate. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol furnished a deep green powder, which decomposed with swelling above 175°, yield 75%. (Found: S, 10.52; $C_{24}H_{44}O_4N_8S_4 \cdot 3C_2H_2O_4$ requires S, 10.11 per cent).

Di-(4-p-ethoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazyl-5-)-phenylmethane (XIII) was prepared from 4-p-ethoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole (4.2 g.), benzaldehyde (0.93 g.) and HCl (conc., 12 c.c.) as described in previous cases and crystallised as a fine light yellow powder, m.p. 210° (decomp.), yield 90%. (Found: S, 12.17. $C_{28}H_{28}O_2N_4S_2$ requires S, 12.12 per cent).

Carbinol Base (XIV) and Dye (oxalate) (XV).—The carbinol base was prepared from the leuco-base by oxidation with lead dioxide; when the oxidation was complete, the colour of the solution was deep green. After basification the colour changed to deep rosy. Crystallisation from alcohol yielded a deep brown compound, m.p. 130°, yield 85%.

The dye was prepared as described in the analogous cases above and it appeared as a blue-green powder, m.p. 195°, yield 60%. (Found: S, 9.90. $C_{28}H_{32}O_4N_8S_4 \cdot 3C_2H_2O_4$ requires S, 9.98 per cent).

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